

**Research Link
Australia**

**Dashboard and LLM
Technical Report**

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Introduction

The Research Link Australia (RLA) project, supported by the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC), aims to bridge gaps in research collaboration by developing a national platform to aggregate, analyse, and share insights about research expertise, outcomes, and partnerships. This report outlines key technical components of the project, including internal and external data, and frontend and backend technology used to form the Analytical Interface Toolkit (AIT), and exploration in use of Large Language Models (LLM) for interrogating the data.

About the data

The RLA project uses two main sources of research data:

- Internal data from Griffith University's Research Information Management System.
- Data from the National Graph Research Graph.

About the internal data

The internal data for the Research Link Australia project is sourced from RIMS and encompasses data from the last three years. Key components of this data include:

1. **Research funding data:** The internal RIMS data includes Australian Research Council (ARC) and National Health and Medical

Research Council (NHMRC) grants, Consultancy and Commercial Research (CCR), and Philanthropic funding records.

2. **Researcher information:** Comprehensive detail about researcher involved in funding, including Chief/Lead Investigators.
3. **Organisational Data:** Organisations associated with grants and researchers.
4. **Linkage through ORCID:** Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID) enables robust linkage of researchers, grants, and organisations.

Further NHMRC data was sourced, refined, and added into the data source, and ranges from 2014 to present.

These internal data contain more comprehensive, unredacted funding records, but do not contain publications data. Records are also limited solely to research connected to Griffith University. The internal RIMS does not store ORCID, and this data had to be manually collected and matched. This data has been normalised and stored in a MySQL database.

About the Research Graph

The National Graph Research Graph is a Neo4j graph database of research collaboration networks within Australia and internationally. This network complements internal data by offering a more diverse view of interconnecting research outputs and organisational dynamics.

Records within the National Graph include:

- **Researchers:** Comprehensive details about researchers, including their affiliations and activities across institutions.
- **Organisations:** Profiles of research, public, and private organisations, and their collaborative networks.
- **Grants:** Detailed insights into funding research projects and their outcomes.

- **Publications and research outputs:** Comprehensive publication and research output data.

Figure 1 Research Graph Schema

The Research Graph schema is shown above in **Figure 1**.

Nodes within the Research Graph are connected via ORCID. Crucially, the Research Graph contains comprehensive publication data, where the internal data does not.

There are data quality issues present in both the internal data and Research Graph, including duplicate data, missing data, and inconsistent standardisation, such as in organisation names.

About the technology

The technology used in RLA enables the exploration of the data through the following dimensions:

- Finding collaborators and experts.
- Funding insights.
- Benchmarking and metrics.
- Identifying strengths and gaps.
- Understanding collaboration dynamics.
- Accessing more comprehensive data.

The technology composes the Analytical Interface Toolkit (AIT), built in Power BI with MySQL and Neo4j databases, and the LLM implementation with Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG), agent-based framework, and vector database for intelligent research data querying.

About the Analytical Interface Toolkit

The AIT is split into two main components:

1. **Backend:** The internal data is queried via a MySQL workbench connector for use within the front end. The Neo4j Research Graph is queried via an API call as an Advanced Query in Power BI and is converted into a

series of relational tables for use in the Power BI data model.

2. **Frontend:** The AIT frontend is built in Power BI. The AIT consists of twenty-five pages of content, composed of visualisations of the two data sources. Visualisations include tabular outputs, network graphs, bar and timeseries charts.

The primary advantage of Power BI as the AIT is security and access control. Internal records are sensitive, and access can be more easily limited in the Power BI service, since only authorised user emails can use an access link, and the sharing of the report and downloading of data can be disabled. Further, while verbose, the use of the API call for the Neo4j database enables the use of Cypher (Neo4j standard graph query language) to query the graph, and the conversion of the data from graph to relational tables, while inconvenient, is automatically handled.

The primary disadvantage of Power BI as the AIT is the inflexibility of the data model. The Neo4j graph database must be converted to relational tables, and more complex querying (for example, finding researchers and their connected to a chosen research or organisation via a research project) necessitates duplicated tables, rather than re-querying extant tables. Further, Power BI necessitates the refresh of all tables whenever any table is modified, even when that modification may be trivial (for example, renaming a column). This results in excessive waiting, as Power BI re-queries from the source for largely unchanged records.

See appendix below for AIT screen captures.

About the Large Language Model

Large Language Models (LLMs) are advanced AI systems that enable natural language interaction with complex data. Our implementation transforms how researchers access institutional data by allowing them to ask

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questions in plain English and receive comprehensive insights.

Key Capabilities

The system provides intelligent insights through natural conversations about:

- **Research Expertise:** Find collaborators and experts across different fields
- **Funding Intelligence:** Track grants, and funding patterns
- **Organisational Networks:** Discover institutional partnerships and collaboration opportunities
- **Research Impact:** Analyse research outputs and strategic opportunities

As demonstrated in Figure 3 a user can simply ask *"Show me Tom Verhelst yearly grant funding trend since 2019"* and receive organised results showing grants and fundings.

System Architecture and Benefits

Our implementation uses an intelligent agent-based architecture where specialised AI components work together to understand and process user queries.

Key features include:

- **Advanced LLM Integration:** Incorporates state-of-the-art language models with up to 405 billion parameters for enhanced understanding and response generation.
- **Retrieval Augmentation:** Enables access to accurate, up-to-date research information beyond standard LLM capabilities.
- **Hybrid Data Handling:** Integrates vector databases for semantic search across research documents with relational databases for structured data.
- **Multi-Agent Coordination:** Facilitates natural language query processing, database interaction, data visualisation, and insight generation.

The modular architecture provides flexibility by supporting:

- Multiple LLM options (open-source and commercial)
- Compatibility with various vector and SQL databases
- Adaptable frontend interfaces for diverse use cases

See appendix below for overall framework.

Resource Requirements

The current development leverages university computing infrastructure, including access to high-performance GPUs, storage capacity, and development environments. While high-performance computing hardware like NVIDIA A100 would typically represent a significant cost, the rapid evolution of LLM technology is driving substantial cost reductions.

Industry leaders like OpenAI have reduced their model hosting costs by up to 83-90% in the past year alone. New optimisation techniques can reduce GPU memory usage by 50%, and batch processing options offer additional 50% cost reductions. These trends suggest continued improvements in cost-efficiency for future scaling and deployment options. In this rapidly evolving field, early adoption and continued development are crucial to maintain competitive advantage in research intelligence capabilities.

Areas for Further Development

The system's evolution requires attention in several key areas:

- Creating high-quality question-SQL pairs requires domain expertise and complex query patterns require extensive examples for accurate handling.

- Field of Research (FoR) codes present significant challenges as research areas evolve (e.g., "AI" now spans multiple codes including machine learning, robotics, and computer vision).
- Historical grants may use outdated FoR codes that don't align with current research classifications.

Conclusion

The technology used in the Research Link Australia project is instrumental to its success. Through a combination of internal and external data sources, and a range of technology including MySQL, Neo4j, Power BI, and AI systems, the RLA project enables powerful exploration of research funding, funders, organisations, and their collaboration networks.

Appendix

Figure 2 Field of Research by funding AIT view

```

//Enter the base URL for the Neo4j Server
let
  __Neo4jURL = "http://localhost:7474",
  // Enter the name of the database in Neo4j
  __Neo4jDatabase = "neo4j",
  // Enter the username for database access in the Neo4j database
  __Username = "neo4j",
  // Enter the user password for databases in the Neo4j database
  __Password = ,
  // Enter a Cypher Query returning full nodes.
  __CypherQuery = "MATCH (g:grant)-[t]-(n:(researcher)-[r:orcid]->(o:organisation {country: 'AU'})) RETURN DISTINCT id(g) as GrantId, g.key",
  // This step makes the HTTP API call to Neo4j to return data in JSON format.
  #"Neo4jResults" =
    Json.Document(
      Web.Contents(__Neo4jURL & "/db/" & __Neo4jDatabase & "/tx/commit",
        [
          Headers =
            [

```

Figure 3 Querying Neo4j graph data using an API Ccall in an Advanced Query in Power BI

You Show me Tom Verhelst yearly grant funding trend since 2019

```
SELECT
  YEAR(startdate) AS grant_year,
  COUNT(*) AS number_of_grants,
  SUM(funding_amount) AS yearly_funding
FROM
  LLM_Version
WHERE
  LOWER(researcher) LIKE LOWER('%Tom Verhelst%')
  AND startdate >= '2019-01-01'
GROUP BY
  YEAR(startdate)
ORDER BY
  grant_year ASC
```

GRANT_YEAR	NUMBER_OF_GRANTS	YEARLY_FUNDING
2021	2	346012
2022	3	414597
2023	6	370560

Tom Verhelst received 2 grants totaling \$346,012 in 2021, 3 grants totaling \$414,597 in 2022, and 6 grants totaling \$370,560 in 2023.

Play

You Update the chart with these instructions: use line chart

Tom Verhelst's Yearly Grant Funding Trend Since 2019

Figure 4 Natural language query example - User asks about Tom Verhelst's grant trends and receives funding data from 2021-2023

Figure 5 System Framework Overview

